

EUROPEAN POLICYBRIEF

DELIVERABLE 7.3 - FINAL TIME4CS POLICY BRIEF

Practical, adaptable, and innovative recommendations for research organisations willing to pursue Institutional Change to integrate Citizen Science and to follow a validated approach. The approach is based on map and analysis of institutional Citizen Science adoptions, the TIME4CS knowledge base framework, and the experience of developing and implementing tailor-made Institutional Roadmaps by TIME4CS partners.

31st December 2023

INTRODUCTION

In the fast-evolving scientific landscape, research organizations must adapt to the complexities of today's world. Integrating Citizen Science (CS) into the research process is a powerful method for achieving this goal. Considered as a fast-growing mode of research and innovation, the benefits of CS extend beyond science to society, empowering citizens as active participants in research, fostering ownership of generated knowledge, enhancing transparency, and contributing to Open Science. CS projects aid in societal acceptance of innovations and understanding science-based policies.

The policy implications deriving from TIME4CS' three years of implementation are aimed at encouraging research organisations to embrace CS through institutional changes, in order for CS to gain relevance in the European context as a whole.

Within this context, some assumptions and drivers have been proven to be crucial in terms of evidence produced by the project for their implications in addressing policy objectives:

- Adopting CS in research organizations requires a cultural shift and a blend of social and organizational approaches. The social approach targets individual mindsets and behaviours, while the organizational approach aims at modifying structures and norms.
- Successful institutional changes for CS involve established projects, participation in networks, CS champions, and strategic plans.
- Sustainable changes should be irreversible, inclusive, comprehensive, and contextualized.

Taking into account those factors and getting inspired from TIME4CS partners successful experiences, research institutions can harness the public engagement to advance knowledge, secure funding, and address

societal issues. Transforming the research ecosystem to embrace CS fosters innovation, collaboration, and inclusivity, benefiting both science and society.

The content of this Policy Brief is meant to complement the D1.4 "TIME4CS statement to encourage Institutional Changes to promote Citizen Science"¹. While the Statement is a document comprising a wide set of cross-sectorial recommendations for research organisations willing to pursue institutional changes to integrate CS, this Policy Brief, given its purpose and scope, pays special attention to the more strictly policy-relevant implications, in particular with regards to research funders as key players in the policy context defined above.

EVIDENCE AND ANALYSIS

Through the project lifecycle, the consortium gathered, examined, and analysed best practices, essential components and enablers for transforming the research ecosystem. This work of knowledge building focused on four key Intervention Areas: 1) Research; 2) Education & Awareness-raising; 3) Support Infrastructure & Resources; and 4) Policy & Assessment. They were also examined in relation to possible actions Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) can take to embed CS, and to support the development and implementation of Institutional roadmaps tailored for each Implementing project partner.

After three years of dedicated work with such institutional roadmaps, the Implementing organizations gained a deeper understanding of institutional arrangements, challenges, resources, and effective strategies for instigating institutional change within their specific contexts. This knowledge played a pivotal role in regularly updating the roadmaps throughout the project's duration. Additionally, it led to the identification of practical recommendations by TIME4CS partners regarding optimal approaches.

Within this framework, while TIME4CS policy recommendations primarily target RPOs in the early stages of CS implementation, they are also directed at Research Funding Organizations (RFOs). The aim is to encourage them to further support effective institutional change in RPOs by designing funding schemes and launching programs that explicitly include CS or integrate it into existing funding structures. It is crucial to apprise funders and policymakers of grassroots CS experiences and requirements to unlock its full potential, including through increased financial and policy support.

The evidence and analyses behind the policy findings and related recommendations presented in this document are clustered around four main pillars, reflecting in turn the interaction and cross-fertilization of TIME4CS interlinked Work Packages:

- **Analysis of CS state of the art and challenges:** the public deliverable D1.3 "Lessons learnt repository of TIME4CS"² gathers and summarises the learnings from D1.2 "Best practices repository of TIME4CS Front Runners"³ and the results from the D1.1 "Collection of case studies of institutional adoption of CS"⁴. These results served as an inspiration for the implementing project partners to identify the key elements, and factors necessary for successful and sustainable institutional change, as well as to reflect on their adaptability to their own baselines, needs and contexts.
- **Development and implementation of roadmap framework leading to institutional changes:** all activities carried out in this sense culminated in the production of the TIME4CS Reflection Tool⁵, a practical guidance for planning concrete actions to be implemented in order to implement

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10201230>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6402090>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5017362>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5807507>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6342147>

institutional changes for CS, but providing also the overviews of TIME4CS partners' experiences and lessons learnt relevant to the statement, including sustainability reflection.

- **Knowledge sharing, mutual learning programme and impact assessment:** this included self-assessment of existing CS policies and practices at the Implementing partners' institutions, as well as development of the set of indicators to evaluate the activities undertaken and assess their impact at both institutional and individual (researchers, other targeted staff members, students) levels (see D5.3 "Final Evaluation and Impact Assessment Report"⁶). The evaluation workshops conducted in each Implementing partner institution at the end of the project, were particularly relevant to the Statement development, as the Implementing partner institutions reflected on their CS journey as a whole, their institutional contexts, needs, barriers, strategies and solutions.
- **Capacity-building within institutions to engage and support CS activities:** valuable training materials have been developed, disseminated and promoted across different channels (see D4.3 "Final version of the Description of TIME4CS training programs"⁷). All materials are openly available for re-use.

POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations resulting from the project's work and findings as defined above are divided into three main areas of work, for each of which the RFOs' perspective will be highlighted below as most relevant in terms of policy needs:

- **Boosting motivation and building capacity for researchers and members of the public to initiate and participate in CS projects**

This part of the recommendations is mainly addressed to RPOs and concrete actions to be implemented in order to show the benefits of CS (i.e. communication campaigns, learning how to develop a CS project, identifying and supporting CS champions in the institution). However, structural measures to be adopted by research funders are relevant in this field as well, since reward mechanisms such as institutional grants may play a crucial role in boosting interest for doing CS.

- **Ensuring funding for CS activities**

Organising CS activities and information events, providing trainings, developing and spreading communication materials as well as other CS-related activities require funds. Main recommendations for research funders are, in this sense:

- to recognise, facilitate and promote the use of CS as a research methodology by designing of funding schemes and launching programmes specific to CS and adapting research funding scheme. Research funders should therefore create or expand funding instruments for CS, adapting to the specific needs and timelines of projects; this includes recognizing startup costs of CS, rewarding participatory methods, and providing long-term funding.
- at national level, to include CS into research funding schemes, either as a specific CS call, by making CS part of regular call, or including CS under the umbrella of wider priority areas (i.e. Open Science and RRI)
- to explore possibilities to make funding more accessible for non-university actors, award both scientists and civil society organisations, encouraging in turn the collaboration between citizens and universities or research centres

- **Developing and implementing personalised Institutional Roadmaps**

This area is mainly related to the definition and adoption of action plans for organisations interested in the institutional adoption of CS (i.e. through the definition of flexible roadmaps following a common framework within the four Intervention Areas identified by TIME4CS). In terms of policy needs, it is important to look at which Grounding Actions have been co-designed and implemented specifically within two of the four

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7486205>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6906329>

TIME4CS Intervention Areas, namely Support resources and infrastructure, and Policy and Assessment (see D2.3 “Final version of the Compilation of the Roadmaps and Grounding Actions for the Implementers”⁸). In fact, under this two areas, the experience of TIME4CS’ partner institutions proves the importance of, among the others, foreseeing funds for CS activities and adopting evaluation criteria for researchers’ evaluation that take CS into account.

SUSTAINABILITY AND LEGACY

These project outputs are available on the TIME4CS Zenodo community at

<https://zenodo.org/communities/time4cs>:

[D1.1 Collection of Case Studies of institutional adoption of Citizen Science](#)

[D1.2 Best practices repository of TIME4CS front-runners](#)

[D1.3 Lesson learnt repository of TIME4CS](#)

[D1.4 TIME4CS statement to encourage Institutional Changes to promote Citizen Science](#)

[D2.1 First version of the Compilation of roadmaps and Grounding Actions for the Implementers – First Version](#)

[Reflection tool for Institutional Changes in Citizen Science](#)

[D4.3 Final version of the Description of TIME4CS training programs](#)

[D5.1 Evaluation and Impact Assessment Plan](#)

Other resources:

[Citizen Science Open Innovation community on Crowdhelix](#)

[TIME4CS Case Studies](#)

[Massive Open Online Course \(MOOC\) with training resources](#)

PROJECT OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGIES

The overall objective of TIME4CS was to facilitate the implementation of sustainable institutional changes in RPOs by promoting Public Engagement (with citizens and citizens associations) and CS in science and technology.

TIME4CS aimed to achieve this in 4 areas that are central to RPOs activities: 1) Research, 2) Education & Awareness-raising, 3) Support resources & Infrastructure, and 4) Policy & Assessment.

For each area, specific Grounding Actions (GAs) were defined by the RPOs to implement, paving the way to systemic institutional changes in terms of public engagement and Citizen Science.

The project methodology is based on knowledge transfer and mutual learning, and involves two main types of actors: Front-Runners and Implementers. The Front-Runners are TIME4CS partner RPOs (UCL, UZH and AU) who have outstanding expertise in CS and have already experienced institutional changes in one or more of the abovementioned IAs. The Implementers are further TIME4CS partners (CRG, UniSR, KTU & T-UCC) who are in the early stages of embracing CS in their organizations, but are dedicated to facilitating institutional changes and to integrate CS in their strategy and work approach.

The process of knowledge transfer is intended to be multidirectional: a dynamic and living exchange of capacity building and mutual learning. The capacity building is tailored to the Implementers’ needs and consists of several training activities (physical and virtual), some open to the public beyond the project’s partners, and aiming at building new capacities and a community of practice around TIME4CS. The mutual learning programme led to the development of a tailored specific action plan for each Implementer (the institutional Roadmap), including a set of specific and detailed actions to implement (GAs).

The whole process is supported by the development, set-up and facilitation of the knowledge transfer approach, the definition and implementation of institutional changes in the institutional Roadmaps and

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5743298>

corresponding GAs, and finally the implementation of a robust evaluation and monitoring framework appraising the effectiveness, impact and validity of the implemented actions by three facilitator partners, APRE, ESF and ZSI.

Finally, as a Science with and for Society (SwafS) funded project, TIME4CS actively engaged with other SwafS projects through regular exchange of information, mutual promotion and dissemination of results, organization of joint activities and through participation in European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) working groups for CS and Open Science projects.

PROJECT IDENTITY

PROJECT NAME Supporting sustainable Institutional Changes to promote Citizen Science in Science and Technology (TIME4CS)

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FUNDING SCHEME

Horizon 2020: SwafS-23-2020 Grounding RRI in society with a focus on citizen science

DURATION

January 2021 – December 2023 (36 months)

BUDGET

EU contribution: 1 499 127.50€.

WEBSITE

<https://www.time4cs.eu>

**FOR MORE
INFORMATION**

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FURTHER READING

All project outputs are available on the TIME4CS website and Zenodo community at:

- <https://www.time4cs.eu>
- <https://zenodo.org/communities/time4cs/>

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